

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ligand-exchange Reactions in *fac*-(Piperidine)[1,2-bis(diphenylphosphino)ethane]tricarbonyl tungsten(0)

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The kinetics and mechanism of piperidine (=pip) displacement from *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃(=R) by a number of phosphine and phosphite ligands (=L) in chlorobenzene, toluene or acetone to afford *fac*-(L)(diphos)W(CO)₃ are reported. This thermal substitution process proceeds via a mechanism which involves reversible dissociation of piperidine from *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ (governed by the rate constants K_1 and K_{-1}) and followed by ligand attack at the resulting [(diphos)W(CO)₃] intermediate (governed by the rate constant K_2). This ligand-exchange reaction proceeds via a ligand-independent path and obeys a rate law, $-d[R]/dt = K_1[R]$. Rate constants and activation parameters in different solvents are reported.

Competitive reactions (pip vs L) for the [(diphos)W(CO)₃] intermediate are also reported. Although there is slight preference for ligands with small Tolman cone angle, the results indicate little discriminating ability for the [(diphos)W(CO)₃] intermediate upon combination with nucleophiles with different steric and electronic factors. The rate constant for W-pip dissociation K_1 exhibits a slight increase with increasing solvent polarity. However, the competition ratio, K_2/K_{-1} seems to have minimal dependency on the polar character of the solvent.

Recently, studies in organometallic chemistry which deals with the reactivity of the solvated five-coordinate intermediates of the type $L_xM(CO)_{5-x}$ (M = Cr, Mo, W; L = amine, phosphine, or phosphite; $x = 0, 1, 2$) have received increasing attention¹. These solvated intermediates are generated thermally in steady-state concentrations, and may also be produced in predominant concentrations via conventional and pulsed laser flash photolysis of the hexacoordinated group-VIB metal carbonyls¹⁻¹³. These studies have proven to be significant to a better understanding of the behaviour of such transients, which are 'models' for the active species in a number of industrially important catalytic processes including hydroformylation, polymerization, and olefin-metathesis¹⁴.

An early study of the reactivity of the five-

coordinate intermediate [Mo(CO)₄(PPh₃)], which was generated thermally through amine dissociation from (amine)Mo(CO)₄(PPh₃) (amine = pyridine, piperidine) in hexane solution, has illustrated the lack of discrimination of this intermediate upon reacting with a variety of Lewis bases¹⁵.

Dobson and coworkers conducted studies of the reactivity and the discriminating ability of a number of those highly reactive five-coordinate transients employing parallel thermal and pulsed laser flash photometric methods^{1,9-12}. For example, the complex *cis*-(pip)(L)W(CO)₄ undergoes thermal ligand-exchange reactions via a mechanism which involves initial W-pip bond-breaking, and thus generates [(L)W(CO)₄] transient, which reacts in solution with various nucleophiles (=L') to afford

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cis-(L)(L')W(CO)₄ as an initial reaction product. This intermediate is also generated through pulsed laser flash photolysis of the complex *cis*-(pip)(L)W(CO)₄. The rate constants for combination of the thermally and photochemically produced [(L)W(CO)₄] transient with a number of Lewis bases, the activation parameters and the competition ratios were also determined and confirmed the nature, photochemical and thermal reactivities of this intermediate.

Recently, we have conducted a parallel thermal and pulsed laser flash photolysis studies of the complex *fac*-(py)(diphos)Mo(CO)₃ (py = pyridine) in toluene solution, and have illustrated the behaviour of the transient [(diphos)Mo(CO)₃] upon combination with various Lewis bases. Reported here are thermal studies of ligand-exchange reactions of *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ in different solvents at various temperatures. Besides, a competitive study of Lewis bases for the (diphos)-W(CO)₃ intermediate is also reported.

Results and Discussion

The observed rate constants and the positive entropies of activation suggest that ligand-exchange reactions of *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ with various Lewis bases (=L) proceed via a unimolecular path which involves rate-determining dissociation of piperidine followed by fast attack of the incoming nucleophile at the resulting [(diphos)W(CO)₃] intermediate and thus, when no piperidine is added, follows the first order rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\textit{fac}\text{-}(\text{pip})(\text{diphos})\text{W}(\text{CO})_3] \quad (1)$$

Under the kinetic conditions employed, reaction product is exclusively *fac*-(L)(diphos)W(CO)₃ as shown in equation (1). This observation, as derived from the characteristic A'+A'+A'' carbonyl stretching frequencies of the corresponding *fac*-products under C_s local symmetry (Table 1), is in full agreement with the assumptions of the principle of microscopic reversibility¹⁶, 'quasi-microscopic reversibility'¹⁷ and also with observations reported

for similar systems^{8,19}. The thermal ligand-exchange reaction proceeds according to equation (2),

(L = phosphines, phosphites; pip = piperidine)

Pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) in different solvents at various temperatures are given in Table 2. First order rate constants, calculated from the rate expression (1), are presented in Table 3. Activation parameters for the unimolecular dissociation of piperidine from the complex *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ are given in Table 4. The results indicate that the first order rate constant (*K*₁) increases with increasing solvent dielectric constant. Similar solvent effect results were also observed by Covey and Brown²⁰ for amine dissociation from (amine)Mo(CO)₅ complexes.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES *fac*-(diphos)W(CO)₃(L)

L	ν _{CO} *(cm ⁻¹)	Analysis:	
		Found/(Calcd)	
		C	H
C ₅ H ₁₁ N	1 919vs, 1 822s, 1 798s	54.62 (54.35)	4.63 (4.69)
P(O-i-C ₃ H ₇) ₃	1 938vs, 1 846s, 1 836s	52.29 (52.19)	5.36 (5.19)
P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃	1 940vs, 1 848s, 1 839s	50.89 (50.50)	4.25 (4.62)
P(OCH ₃) ₃	1 941vs, 1 851s, 1 842s	49.08 (48.69)	4.70 (4.21)
P(OCH ₂) ₃ CCH ₃	1 950vs, 1 864s, 1 852s	50.47 (50.14)	4.42 (4.08)
P(OC ₆ H ₅) ₃	1 952vs, 1 868s, 1 855s	58.21 (57.81)	4.28 (4.03)
P(C ₆ H ₅) ₃	1 935vs, 1 841s,b	60.48 (60.79)	4.55 (4.23)
Sb(C ₆ H ₅) ₃	1 936vs, 1 844s,b		

* 1,2-Dichloroethane solution; s = strong, vs = very strong, b = broad.

TABLE 2—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THERMAL REACTIONS OF THE COMPLEXES *fac*-(pip)(diphos) W(CO)₃ WITH L (L = PHOSPHINE AND PHOSPHITES) AND PIPERIDINE IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

L	T °C	[L] (M)	[pip] (M)	[pip]/[L] × 10 ⁵	<i>K</i> _{obs} s ⁻¹	Table-2 (Contd.)						
In chlorobenzene : P(O-i-C ₃ H ₇) ₃	49.5	0.084 5	0	0	94.6(8)	P(OCH ₂) ₃ CCH ₃	0.038 9	0	0	7.52(5)		
		0.162	0	0	90.2(5)		0.127	0	0	7.63(11)		
		0.233	0	0	92.7(9)		0.105	0.017 6	0.168	6.78(5)		
		0.055	0	0	29.5(8)		0.121	0.026 9	0.222	6.48(8)		
		0.271	0	0	27.2(4)		0.165	0.059 6	0.361	6.02(12)		
	40.2	0.310	0	0	28.8(5)		0.194	0.086 1	0.444	5.61(3)		
		0.149	0	0	15.8(8)		0.238	0.134	0.563	5.36(8)		
		0.272	0	0	15.3(4)		0.211	0.141	0.668	5.08(14)		
		0.306	0	0	15.1(7)		0.242	0.189	0.781	4.70(6)		
		0.082 6	0	0	7.69(4)		0.301	0.267	0.887	4.52(4)		
	36.4	0.145	0	0	7.70(8)		0.362	0.339	0.936	4.38(14)		
		0.439	0	0	7.66(3)		0.164	0	0	7.88(7)		
		0.024 1	0.001 00	0.041 5	6.98(5)		0.282	0	0	7.72(9)		
		0.026 8	0.002 20	0.082 1	6.45(9)		0.017 5	0.002 01	0.115	6.12(4)		
		0.032 7	0.005 11	0.156	5.62(3)		0.036 3	0.008 61	0.237	4.98(8)		
	P(OCH ₃) ₃	31.1	0.035 5	0.070 2	0.198	5.18(9)		0.126	0.037 3	0.296	4.62(2)	
			0.046 8	0.012 3	0.263	4.83(7)		0.139	0.051 2	0.368	4.05(12)	
			0.042 1	0.014 2	0.337	4.31(1)		0.128	0.054 3	0.424	3.85(5)	
			0.056 3	0.023 7	0.421	3.92(3)		0.154	0.078 2	0.508	3.50(1)	
			0.058 0	0.032 9	0.567	3.25(1)		0.225	0.156	0.693	3.01(6)	
P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃		0.058 6	0.039 0	0.666	2.98(4)		0.248	0.178	0.718	2.84(13)		
		0.059 8	0.044 7	0.747	2.82(6)		0.336	0.296	0.881	2.62(7)		
		0.061 1	0.054 5	0.892	2.43(7)		0.351	0.335	0.954	2.38(5)		
		0.042 5	0	0	7.62(9)		0.155	0	0	7.78(8)		
		0.179	0	0	7.42(7)		0.263	0	0	7.59(3)		
		0.025 3	0.001 35	0.053 3	7.23(6)		0.016 2	0.003 26	0.201	5.69(7)		
		0.036 2	0.003 13	0.086 5	6.95(3)		0.018 7	0.005 33	0.285	5.08(4)		
		0.038 2	0.004 16	0.109	6.84(5)		0.114	0.040 9	0.359	4.59(9)		
		0.059 2	0.111	0.188	6.36(2)		0.135	0.058 5	0.433	4.36(11)		
		0.079 2	0.020 9	0.264	5.95(1)		0.144	0.082 9	0.576	3.72(7)		
P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃	49.5	0.138	0.050 8	0.368	5.39(4)		0.201	0.137	0.682	3.50(8)		
		0.205	0.117	0.572	4.77(9)		0.222	0.163	0.734	3.31(6)		
		0.238	0.165	0.693	4.41(6)		0.284	0.224	0.789	3.21(2)		
		0.312	0.244	0.782	4.20(7)		0.235	0.197	0.838	2.99(4)		
		0.355	0.304	0.856	3.96(3)		0.246	0.222	0.902	2.85(9)		
		0.362	0.342	0.942	3.82(8)		0.268	0.258	0.963	2.78(4)		
		0.033	0.000	0.000	7.75(8)		0.114	0	0	7.85(9)		
		0.149	0.000	0.000	7.45(4)		0.204	0	0	7.66(4)		
		0.025 5	0.002 22	0.087	6.92(4)		0.046 2	0.002 22	0.048 1	7.44(8)		
		0.043 1	0.004 87	0.113	6.59(5)		0.048 1	0.003 46	0.071 9	7.30(5)		
P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃	40.2	0.118	0.025 1	0.213	5.98(4)		0.054 2	0.007 91	0.146	6.78(3)		
		0.168	0.047 0	0.280	5.56(9)		0.086 5	0.017 6	0.203	6.42(12)		
		0.204	0.094 1	0.461	4.72(2)		0.103	0.033 1	0.321	5.84(11)		
		0.222	0.147	0.662	4.18(12)		0.146	0.061 2	0.419	5.45(7)		
		0.215	0.177	0.823	3.58(7)		0.181	0.113	0.624	4.74(8)		
		0.302	0.274	0.907	3.45(10)		0.198	0.161	0.813	4.06(4)		
		In toluene : P(O-i-C ₃ H ₇) ₃	49.5	0.117	0	0	80.5(6)		0.046 2	0.002 22	0.048 1	7.44(8)
				0.199	0	0	86.2(7)		0.048 1	0.003 46	0.071 9	7.30(5)
				0.278	0	0	82.6(9)		0.054 2	0.007 91	0.146	6.78(3)
				0.088 2	0	0	23.6(5)		0.086 5	0.017 6	0.203	6.42(12)
0.167	0			0	21.9(4)		0.103	0.033 1	0.321	5.84(11)		
0.167	0			0	21.9(4)		0.146	0.061 2	0.419	5.45(7)		

Table-2 (Contd.)

	0.227	0	0	22.9(8)	
31.1	0.135	0	0	5.62(9)	
	0.186	0	0	5.99(3)	
	0.259	0	0	5.91(14)	
	0.023 9	0.003 18	0.133	4.81(3)	
	0.32 5	0.008 61	0.265	4.06(6)	
	0.115	0.037 3	0.324	3.72(13)	
	0.052 3	0.018 4	0.352	3.65(7)	
	0.061 2	0.028 2	0.461	3.31(2)	
	0.127	0.070 5	0.555	3.12(8)	
	0.182	0.113	0.621	2.89(4)	
	0.196	0.134	0.684	2.82(11)	
	0.230	0.168	0.730	2.71(9)	
	0.263	0.203	0.772	2.61(6)	
	0.307	0.271	0.883	2.45(14)	
	0.311	0.287	0.923	2.22(5)	
In acetone :					
P(O-i-C ₃ H ₇) ₃	40.2	0.091 2	0	0	31.6(4)
		0.117	0	0	30.6(9)
		0.242	0	0	33.1(5)
36.4		0.162	0	0	19.6(7)
		0.209	0	0	19.2(6)
		0.288	0	0	18.8(3)
31.1		0.082 3	0	0	9.28(3)
		0.175	0	0	9.62(8)
		0.301	0	0	9.18(6)
		0.026 5	0.004 68	0.177	7.02(4)
		0.046 6	0.010 3	0.197	6.62(8)
		0.044 4	0.012 8	0.288	5.99(5)
		0.122	0.043 3	0.355	5.62(4)
		0.143	0.056 1	0.392	5.42(2)
		0.164	0.017 3	0.435	5.04(9)
		0.205	0.137	0.668	4.25(7)
		0.238	0.172	0.723	3.86(11)
		0.265	0.207	0.781	3.73(4)
		0.286	0.235	0.822	3.65(5)
		0.309	0.307	0.994	3.33(8)

TABLE 3—COMPETITION RATIOS WITH PIPERIDINE AND FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR REACTIONS OF *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ WITH L IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

L	T °C	$\times 10^5 k_1^*$ s ⁻¹	$\times 10^5 k_1^{**}$ s ⁻¹	k_2/k_{-1}
P(O-i-C ₃ H ₇) ₃	31.1 ^a	7.68(2)	7.63(9)	0.43(2)
	36.4 ^a	15.4(4)	—	—
	40.2 ^a	29(1)	—	—
	49.5 ^a	93(2)	—	—
P(OCH ₃) ₃	31.1 ^a	7.52(1)	7.61(3)	0.96(1)
P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃	31.1 ^a	7.60(2)	7.70(6)	0.73(1)
P(OCH ₂) ₂ CCH ₃	31.1 ^a	7.58(6)	7.68(8)	1.26(4)
P(OC ₆ H ₅) ₃	31.1 ^a	7.8(1)	7.7(2)	0.42(2)

Table-3 (Contd.)

P(C ₆ H ₅) ₃	31.1 ^a	7.7(1)	7.86(2)	0.53(3)
P(C ₆ H ₅) ₃	31.1 ^a	7.8(1)	7.90(4)	0.90(1)
P(O-i-C ₃ H ₇) ₃	31.1 ^b	5.8(2)	5.61(9)	0.68(2)
	40.2 ^b	22.8(9)	—	—
	49.5 ^b	83(3)	—	—
	31.1 ^c	9.4(2)	9.1(2)	0.56(3)
	36.4 ^c	19.2(4)	—	—
	40.2 ^c	31.8(1)	—	—

* Determined directly from kinetics runs employing no piperidine.

** Determined from intercepts of plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[pip]/[L]$.
Solvent : ^aChlorobenzene, ^btoluene, ^cacetone.

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR REACTION OF *fac*-(pip)(diphos)(CO)₃ WITH TRIISOPROPYLPHOSPHITE IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S_1^\ddagger$ eu.
Toluene	27.6 +/- 0.1	13.6 +/- 0.1
Chlorobenzene	26.0 +/- 0.1	8.9 +/- 2.1
Acetone	24.7 +/- 0.2	4.5 +/- 0.7

Competitive reactions for the five-coordinate intermediate [(diphos)W(CO)₃] were studied by employing simultaneously large excess of both (L) and piperidine. In this case, the rate of reaction is expressed by equation (3),

$$\text{Rate} = (K_1 K_2 [L] / K_{-1} [pip] + K_2 [L]) [R] = K_{obs} [R] \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) can be rearranged to equation (4),

$$1/K_{obs} = 1/K_1 + (K_{-1}/K_1 K_2) [(pip)/(L)] \quad (4)$$

Plots of $1/K_{obs}$ vs (pip)/(L) (Fig. 1) are linear

Fig. 1. Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[pip]/[L]$ for reactions of the complex *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ with L and piperidine in chlorobenzene at 31.1° : (●) P(OCH₂)₂CCH₃, (○) P(OCH₃)₃, (△) P(OC₂H₅)₃, (×) P(C₆H₅)₃

Fig 2 Plots of $1/K_{obs}$ vs $[pip]/[P(O-i-C_3H_7)_3]$ for reactions of *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ with trisopropylphosphite and piperidine in various solvents at 31.1° : (o) acetone, (●) chlorobenzene, (.) toluene.

with a slope of K_{-1}/K_1K_2 and an intercept of $1/K_1$, which indicate that the proposed mechanism is in fact operative. The value of intercept/slope = K_2/K_{-1} represents the 'competition ratio' for bimolecular rate constants of interaction of the ligand (L) and piperidine with the five-coordinate intermediate (diphos)W(CO)₃ after W-pip bond-breaking as presented in equation (2). These competition ratios, together with values of first order rate constant K_1 in different solvents, are given in Table 3. Thus this ligand-exchange process proceeds via a first order rate law (*vide supra*), and thus is independent of the identity of L. Plots of $1/K_{obs}$ vs $(pip)/(L)$ should have the same intercept regardless of the nature of the incoming nucleophile L. This is in fact the case as shown in Fig. 1. Values of K_1 as determined from the intercepts (Figs. 1 and 2) fit nicely with those determined directly through thermal kinetic of ligand-exchange in *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ employing (L) but $(pip) = 0$.

The competition ratio K_2/K_{-1} should in fact measure the discriminating ability of the [(diphos)W(CO)₃] intermediate towards combination with various nucleophiles with different steric and electronic properties. Values of competition ratio (K_2/K_{-1}) (Table 3) follow the order : $P(OCH_2)_3CCH_3 > P(OCH_2)_3Sb(C_6H_5)_3 > P(OC_2H_5)_3 > P(C_6H_5)_3 > P(O-i-C_3H_7)_3 = P(OC_6H_5)_3$. Although

the results indicate that the [(diphos)W(CO)₃] intermediate exhibits some preference to ligands with small size, the observed order of competition ratios does not seem to reflect the steric or the electronic properties, based on Tolman cone angles and electronic parameters²¹ of these ligands in a conclusive way. The results indicate that both steric and electronic properties of the incoming nucleophiles L are in fact important factors to the reactivity of such ligands. This conclusion is in agreement with results obtained for interaction of Lewis bases with five-coordinate intermediates such as [(diphos)MO(CO)₃] in toluene solution¹², and intermediate $\{[P(O-i-C_3H_7)_3]W(CO)_4\}$ in chlorobenzene solution¹¹.

It is well-documented that intermediates of the type $L_xM(CO)_{5-x}$ (M = Cr, Mo, W; X = 0, 1, 2) undergo rapid solvation/desolvation equilibria in solution²⁻¹². The intermediate [Cr(CO)₅] produced through photolysis of Cr(CO)₆ undergoes fast solvation, in which the solvent occupies a specific site in the coordination sphere, and such solvation processes take place in the picosecond time scale⁵. Solvent effect studies have presented as evidence to the nature of this solvation/desolvation process and have confirmed that activation energies for solvation are very small²². Thus, based on Hammond's postulate²³ the solvated intermediate should resemble the naked five-coordinate species. Solvation/desolvation studies on the transient [(L)W(CO)₄] have illustrated that solvent displacement from *fac*-(solvent)[P(O-i-C₃H₇)₃]-W(CO)₄ (solvent : chlorobenzene) takes place via a pathway involving rate-determining unimolecular dissociation of solvent rather than via an interchange mechanism¹¹. These studies also illustrate that ligand attack occurs at the naked intermediate via a bimolecular mechanism rather than via a dissociative-interchange process¹¹. A similar mechanism was also proposed for combination of the transient [(diphos)MO(CO)₃] with various Lewis bases¹².

Competition studies for the intermediate [(diphos)W(CO)₃] in solvents with different polarities have presented no significant change

in the competition K_2/K_{-1} (Table 3). Although it is conceivable that factors which affect piperidine attack at the five-coordinate intermediate (governed by rate constant K_{-1}) should also affect L attack at this unsaturated transient (governed by rate constant K_2), and a noticeable difference in the competition ratios should be expected in solvents with different polarities if ligand-exchange takes place at the solvated five-coordinate intermediate $fac\text{-}(S)(diphos)W(CO)_3$, (S = chlorobenzene, toluene, acetone), since the W-S bond strength should play some role in determining the bimolecular rate constants by which piperidine and L react. That the competition ratios remain constant within experimental error in solvents with different polar characters, it is thus reasonable to propose that ligand attack takes place at the naked five-coordinate intermediate $(diphos)W(CO)_3$ as given in equation (5),

S = chlorobenzene, toluene, acetone.

Activation parameters are given in Table 4. Entropies of activation are positive as expected for a dissociative mechanism. However, the results indicate less positive entropies of activation in more polar solvents, implying that less disorder upon W-pip bond-breaking is taking place as solvent polarity increases. This observation may indicate some interaction with the solvent in the transition state and thus leading to the formation of the solvated intermediate²⁴. The enthalpy of activation seems to follow a reverse order as compared to the order observed for entropy changes. The observed increase in the value of the first order rate constant (K_1) in more polar solvents

is thus attributed to smaller enthalpy of activation during W-pip bond-breaking in solvents with higher dielectric constants.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1710 FT spectrophotometer and ultraviolet spectra on a Pye-Unican SP8-100 spectrophotometer.

Tungsten hexacarbonyl (Aldrich) was used as obtained. The following solvents and ligands were purified as described elsewhere⁴⁻⁶: trimethylphosphite, triethylphosphite, triisopropylphosphite, triphenylstibine (Aldrich); triphenylphosphine (B.D.H.); chlorobenzene, toluene, acetone, tetrahydrofuran (Fisher). The ligand 'constrained phosphite', 4-methyl-2,6,7-trioxa-1-phosphabicyclo-[2,2,2]octane was prepared and purified according to literature procedure²⁵. The complex $(diphos)\text{-}W(CO)_4$ was prepared and purified as previously reported²⁶.

$fac\text{-}(pip)(diphos)W(CO)_3$: $(Diphos)W(CO)_4$ (6.8 g, 10 mmol) was dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran (300 ml) and the solution was irradiated for about 2 h under nitrogen (Griffin Hg-lamp). The resulting bright yellow solution was stirred with piperidine (15 ml) for about 1 h. The solvent and excess piperidine were then completely removed under reduced pressure at room temperature. The solid residue was then dissolved in toluene (100 ml) and filtered over cold n-hexane (150 ml) and the resulting bright yellow crystals were dried under reduced pressure.

$fac\text{-}(PPh_3)(diphos)W(CO)_3$: A mixture of $fac\text{-}(pip)(diphos)W(CO)_3$ (3.7 g, 5 mmol) and triphenylphosphine (1.8 g, 7 mmol) was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere in chlorobenzene (100 ml) at 80° for about 2 h. The resulting colourless solution was filtered hot over cold hexane (200 ml). The colourless product that precipitated upon cooling in a freezer (-20°) was washed several times with warm hexane (40°) and dried under reduced pressure.

A similar procedure was applied to prepare the complexes *fac*-(L)(diphos)W(CO)₃; L = P(OMe)₃, P(O-*i*-Pr)₃, P(OEt)₃, Sb(PPh)₃, P(OCH₂)₃CCH₃. Carbonyl stretching frequencies and elemental analyses for these complexes are presented in Table 1.

Thermal kinetic studies : The rates of reactions of the substrate *fac*-(pip)(diphos)W(CO)₃ with various ligands at different temperatures were followed by monitoring the decrease in absorbance of the reaction solution at 420 nm. Kinetic runs were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions (at least twentyfive-fold excess of the ligand L). In competitive reactions, large excess of both piperidine and L were also employed to ensure pseudo-first order conditions in both pip and L. Rate constants were obtained through data analysis employing a linear least-squares program²⁷. Plots of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ vs time were linear to about 85% completion, where A_t is the absorbance at time t and A_∞ is the absorbance at infinite time. Competition studies for the intermediate (diphos)-W(CO)₃ were conducted as described elsewhere⁷. Since solutions of the substrate are very sensitive to light, all measurements were taken in the dark. Substrate concentration employed was about 5×10^{-4} M. Limits of error are given in parentheses as the uncertainty of last digit(s) cited to one standard deviation.

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